

**APPLYING AWARENESS-RAISING TASKS FOR
LEARNERS' DIVERGENCE**

Jabborkhonova Nargizakhon Abdumalik kizi

ESL/ESP Instructor

Ajou University in Tashkent

njabborkhonova@mail.ru

Acquiring a foreign language is not only just mastering grammar structures and producing them but also gaining a pragmatic competence that enables learners to understand and be understood appropriately by the speakers of the target language without being insensitive (Gomez-Laich, 2016). However, despite the good instruction and the total immersion of the target language, sometimes learners cannot or reject the appropriate pragmatic use. This phenomenon which is called divergence has several potential causes which prevent gaining native-like pragmatic competence.

Mostly, learners' limited L2 grammatical ability has a negative effect on pragmatic competence. According to Ishihara and Cohen (2010), in order to understand the intended meaning of the speech better, the listener should also be acquainted with the grammar structure of the message. It means that if the learner cannot understand the message due to the unfamiliar grammar form in the target language, it may cause misunderstandings. For example, if the learner can make just direct requests by using simple sentences such as "Open the door," compound sentences such as "Would you mind opening the door?" may be challenging to understand.

According to my observation, students who don't fully acquire the target language's grammar usually face pragmatic failure.

The next widely noticed divergence is the overgeneralization of L2 pragmatic norms. Like grammar rules, learners usually overgeneralize pragmatic norms of the L2 (Ishihara & Cohen, 2010). This misconception usually occurs due to the inappropriate application of L2 norms that learners are prejudiced. With one sentence, we can say pragmatic overgeneralization as using one norm in all situations. In such cases, learners usually ignore different components of L2 such as (culture, society, situation, etc.). For instance, in requiring something in situations that demand high formality, a learner may say, "Give me" Here the structure of the direct request is overgeneralized. Moreover, the pragmatic failure may happen at the linguistic level since learners may confuse the formality level by its length. For example, the short expression "Might I..." which is highly formal, may be considered informal.

As mentioned in Ishihara and Cohen (2010), teachers should apply form-focused activities to overcome divergence caused by limited grammatical ability. For example, in teaching making more polite requests through compound structures, teachers should address the grammar form explicitly. Alcon-Soler (2005) and Cohen (2005) strongly believe that applying an explicit approach in grammar instruction prevents pragmatic failure.

I would be if you could/would +V1

I would be obliged if you could receive the invitation

I would appreciate if you would inform Julia about meeting

Moreover, using deductive instruction in teaching the structure of if-clause to make requests would be appropriate. Because to fully comprehend such complex structures, first, students should be introduced to the form. Then they have to link the form with meaning and use and practice it (Glaiser, 2016).

When it comes to the subsequent divergence - pragmatic overgeneralization, it can be prevented by introducing one pragmatic norm with several opposite examples. For example:

Situation: You are a manager at a big company. You had a very urgent meeting. But, in the morning you were stuck in a heavy traffic jam that's why you were late for the meeting for 40 minutes. When you came, it has already finished. Your boss is furious, in this situation you have to apologize for your late arrival.

a) M: Excuse me

B: Why are you late?

M: I had problems with transportation

b) M: Good morning Mr...I'm really sorry for being late

B: Why are you late?

M: There was a very heavy traffic jam in the morning. That's why it took me 40 minutes to get there. It wouldn't be repeated.

In applying such awareness-raising tasks, an inductive approach is used. Because in this activity students themselves should notice the suitable language use.

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